

THE IMPACT OF QUALITY CULTURE ON GREEN ORGANIZATIONAL IDENTITY IN PRIVATE JORDANIAN UNIVERSITIES: THE MODERATING ROLE OF JOB SATISFACTION

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Abstract

The aim of this study was to determine the impact of quality culture on building a green organizational identity. This study also examined the moderating role of job satisfaction in the relationship between quality culture and green organizational identity in Private Jordanian Universities. This study's population consisted of Deans of Colleges, Heads of academic departments and Unit directors in these universities. A questionnaire was used as a tool to collect data. An appropriate sample of 140 individuals was taken. SPSS software was used to analyze 98 questionnaires that were collected. One of the most important findings of this study was the presence of a statistically significant effect of quality culture on green organizational identity. This study also revealed the moderating role of job satisfaction in the relationship between quality culture and the Green Organizational Identity. The recommendations from this study include encouraging administrators of Private Jordanian Universities to give priority and importance to spreading a quality culture that supports building a green organizational identity that is also keen on raising the level of job satisfaction amongst employees in Private Jordanian Universities in order to improve the image of their green organizational identity. Universities should also incorporate environmental concerns in their vision and strategies in a way that enhances their level of evaluation and raises their level of competitiveness.

Keywords: Quality Culture, Green Organizational Identity, Job Satisfaction, Private Jordanian Universities.

INTRODUCTION

Culture plays a pivotal role in influencing the lives of individuals and societies. Culture reflects the totality of the main values, beliefs, and orientations on which the lives of individuals are based. Therefore, the topic of culture is of great importance when studying human nature, societies and civilizations.

The uncertainty that surrounds the business environment in addition to the unlimited complexities, needs, and desires of consumers has made the interest in environmental management be taken more seriously than in the past by business organizations in general and higher education institutions in particular. Quality culture is now considered a basic foundation that relies on human resource as a driver of creativity and innovation (Xiexiang & Liping, 2011).

Therefore, organizations' orientation towards quality culture will enhance the sustainability of their activities (Lagrosen & Lagrosen, 2019) and improve the image of their green identity especially with the challenge of a fierce competition in the marketplace. Business organizations, including private universities face many challenges that require greater effectiveness and efficiency in order to constantly come up with creative ideas that serve environmental sustainability and create a sustainable competitive advantage (Ones & Dilchert, 2012).

Quality culture has many determinants including country culture, which consists of the shared values and beliefs of a society. Quality culture is also determined by organizational culture, which is the values, beliefs, of an organization that are shared by its employees. Organizational culture is also usually the philosophy of the organization's founder (Nam & Kim, 2011).

Organizational culture is also the extent to which management and employees are aware of the importance of quality culture in their organizations (Xiaxiang & Liping, 2011). In addition, organizational culture serves the strategic direction of organizations. Further, building a supportive quality culture will enhance employees' loyalty to their organizations (Razali et al., 2018).

This in turn will lead to building a strong organizational identity among employees (Bingol et al., 2013). A supportive culture will also enhance employee loyalty to the community surrounding the organization.

This study seeks to achieve the following objectives through its application on Private Jordanian Universities: Identify the level of quality culture in Private Jordanian Universities. Identify the level of green organizational identity in Private Jordanian Universities. Examine the impact of quality culture in building a green organizational identity in Private Jordanian Universities. Examining the moderating role of job satisfaction in the relationship between quality culture and green organizational identity in Private Jordanian Universities.

The importance of this study stems from the fact that it addresses a vital topic at the international organizational level in general and at the Jordanian organizational level in particular. This study will enhance the competitiveness and help in maintaining the sustainability of the universities that were examined in this study as well as other universities.

This study therefore represents a scientific methodological addition to theoretical literature in this field. To the researchers' knowledge this research is considered the first of its kind at the level of Jordanian Universities that addresses the role of quality culture and green organizational identity in Private Jordanian Universities.

The results of this study will also contribute to directing those in charge of Private Jordanian Universities towards enhancing quality culture and raising the level of employee satisfaction in these universities in a way that facilitates the building of a green organizational identity for these institutions.

Study Problem:

Environmental considerations have emerged as a source of interest for many international organizations and are an integral part of the trends of contemporary entrepreneurial organizations.

Environmental management in addition to building a supportive quality culture are now taken into account when organizations build their strategies. Higher education institutions in general and private universities in particular are considered among the most prominent sectors influencing societies in which they carry out their academic missions.

The educational outcomes of higher education institutions are considered major inputs in all economic sectors. This increases the importance of highlighting a green organizational identity in these universities by building an influential quality culture and creating job satisfaction in their employees who will then be keen in improving and adopting this identity.

The above will also increase the competitive advantage of private universities and raise the level of their global classification or ranking, which are now determined most importantly by the level of a university's green organizational identity. The problem of this study can be formulated by the following main question:

What is the role of quality culture in building green organizational identity in Private Jordanian Universities?

The following sub-questions emerged from the main question.

What is the level of green organizational identity in Private Jordanian Universities? What is the level of quality culture in Private Jordanian Universities? Can employee satisfaction moderate the relationship between quality culture and green organizational identity in Private Jordanian Universities?

Hypotheses and Study Model:

Based on this study's problems and objectives and through reviewing the literature related to the variables of this study, the researchers built a study model (Figure 1). The study hypotheses were presented in their null form, at a significance level of ($\alpha = 0.05$) as follows:

Ho1: There is no statistically significant effect of the dimensions of quality culture (customer orientation, employee orientation, higher management commitment, continuous improvement, process orientation) on green organizational identity in Private Jordanian Universities.

Ho2: There is no statistically significant effect of quality culture on organizational identity with job satisfaction as a moderating variable in Private Jordanian Universities.

Figure 1: Study Model

Source: Prepared by the researchers based on literature on the subject.

Theoretical Framework:

Quality Culture:

According to (Hofstede, 2010) culture is defined as “the mental programming of the individual that is coordinated and arranged by family and society with a set of values and beliefs that are transmitted by individuals from generation to another”. The concept of culture is a relative concept that differs from one society to another. (Tursyn et al., 2013) explained that all world cultures are a mixture of local or national cultures of each society.

As for organizational culture, Schemarborn (2011) defined it as “a system of values and beliefs shared by those working in the organization where this system grows within a single organization”.

Many studies have emphasized the importance of organizational culture in different organizations, where the success of the organization is attributed to the presence of a strong organizational culture directed towards the organization’s goals (Bauer & Erdogan, 2012). Therefore, organizational culture is considered one of the most important administrative concepts. (Bitici et al., 2006) suggested that there is a strong relationship between performance and organizational culture.

Organizational culture consists of many elements, the most important of which are the following: Organizational values: which are defined as “the basic beliefs and assumptions that guide human behavior and through which one can base judgements about right and

wrong” (Hassan, 2007). Organizational beliefs: which are described as “Shared ideas about the nature of work and social life within the scope of work and how to accomplish work and organizational tasks”. Organizational norms: which are defined as “a set of values and beliefs that provide rules that bind individuals to the organization” (Eng, 2006). Rituals: are activities that are represented on an ongoing basis that express and reinforce the organization’s core values (Robbins et al., 2008: 57).

Symbols and artifacts: are the tangible material framework of organizational culture and consists of the total tangible equipment, the organization’s logo, uniforms, equipment, computers, and anything that is tangible to individuals that distinguish the organization from other organizations (Robbins & Judge, 2007:580; Robbins et al., 2008:57).

According to Berings, Quality culture encompasses several elements of quality which includes values, beliefs, commitment, expectation, agreement and others. (Berings, et al., 2010).

According to previous studies (Sila & Ebrahimpour, 2002; Cronemyr et al., 2017; Ingelsson et al., 2018), the main quality culture values are: customer orientation, management commitment, employee orientation, continuous improvement, and process orientation. This study adopted these five dimensions of quality culture.

Dimensions of Quality Culture:

Quality culture includes basic pillars or dimensions that will be addressed as follows:

Customer Orientation:

Relationships with customers are one of the most important goals that various organizations focus on. Having strong relationships with customer’s leads to building a strong customer base and a larger market share. Therefore, placing relationships with customers as one of the foundations and elements on which organizational culture is based makes the organization’s members more motivated and willing to commit to the values of an orientation towards relationships with customers (Mobarakeh, 2011). Customer orientation is defined as “A set of beliefs that puts the customer at the center” (Aydin and Ceylan, 2011).

Orientation towards Employees:

De Bussy and Suprawan (2012) defined employee orientation as “the organization’s tendency to engage in dialogic communication with its employees.” Relationships with employees plays a major role in the cohesion of the organization and creating the ability to achieve common goals among employees. The orientation and focus on employees provides a great deal of motivation for them to achieve goals and form a distinct organizational culture (Carmeli & Tishler, 2004). de Bussy & Suprawan,(2012) confirmed that employee orientation is one of the most important goals of social responsibility for organizations and that attention paid to employees will have a significant impact on raising their efficiency (Varghese & Edward, 2017).

Management Commitment:

The process of higher management commitment is considered one of the most important values for adopting a quality culture as it expresses the extent to which managers and senior employees in the organization demonstrate commitment to quality culture (Javed, 2015). Higher management commitment plays an important role in activating and supporting quality practices in organizations. Higher management commitment also allows for the creation and dissemination of quality values in all aspects and activities of the organization (Cronemyr et al., 2017).

Continuous Improvement:

Van assen, (2019) emphasized the importance of continuous improvement as one of the elements of quality culture and comprehensive quality. It is worth noting that the continuous improvement approach, which began in Japan (Kaizen), is based on the radical improvement of processes and is also limited to improvement of processes and activities within the organization (Costa et al., 2019).

Process Orientation:

Process orientation is defined as “the degree to which employees pay attention to work activities and tasks in the organization (Cleven et al., 2016). Therefore, process orientation is defined as “a set of organized and measured activities with specific results for the customer or market” (Chen et al., 2009), and is based on the extent of management’s interest in the practical activities and tasks required to achieve the organization’s goals.

Job Satisfaction:

Job satisfaction is considered one of the very important administrative topics that has been extensively studied in administrative sciences literature. Job satisfaction is considered one of the most important factors for understanding work motivation and employee effectiveness (Shaju & Subhashini, 2017). Due to the importance of job satisfaction in increasing employees’ loyalty to their organizations (Marič et al., 2011) and increasing their work performance (Ayodele & Olorunsola, 2012), and according to (Thiagaraj & Thangaswamy, 2017) job satisfaction is “the individual’s attitude towards his job in the presence of an emotional state resulting from the individual’s evaluation of his job in terms of it achieving value in his life.”

According to (Siahaan, 2017), job satisfaction is measured by the employees’ perception of the extent to which their jobs provide aspects that fulfill themselves. The following are factors that affect job satisfaction: Environmental factors: These include work conditions, reward and incentive systems, supervision and leadership systems, and the cooperative environment among employees (Belias & Koustelios, 2014; Yang, et al., 2011).

Personal factors: are represented by gender, educational level, and personal and psychological characteristics (González et al., 2016; Aydin et al., 2012). Many studies, such as (Hauff et al., 2015), have confirmed that work characteristics play a role in job satisfaction. Job satisfaction is greatly affected by the extent to which employees feel that

their organization is interested in them and in providing them incentives, wages, rewards, and promotions (Rafiq et al., 2017). Researchers have divided job satisfaction into two main types: emotional satisfaction and cognitive satisfaction (Siahaan, 2017).

Green Organizational Identity:

Organizational identity is a tool for analyzing change and transformations in universities (Dumay et al., 2017; MacDonald, 2013; Stensaker, 2015; Weerts et al., 2014). Organizational identity is also considered a means of ensuring organizational cohesion, as it is the best transmitter of the organization's image to the outside world. It can also be considered a strategic arm on which the organization relies on to what the university should be in the future (Dumay et al., 2017; Aurand, 2001; Judson et al., 2004).

Albert & Whettens (1985) is one of the first to research organizational identity and which most subsequent scholars have relied on for their studies. One of the most prominent criticisms of Albert & Whettens is that they regard organizational identity as permanent and unified. Studies have proven that organizational identity is constantly changing (Gioia et al., 2010; Meyer et al., 2002, Skalen, 2004). Organizational identity is a powerful indicator and mirror that easily reflects what external audiences perceive the organization's name to be (Noh & Tolbert, 2019). Therefore, the application of environmental management and the effective use of resources enhances the university's green image, which will then increase its competitive advantage (Chen, 2011, Noh & Tolbert, 2019).

Key stakeholders in organizations, such as customers, investors, and employees have realized the importance of environmental issues and have become aware of the importance of boycotting organizations with irresponsible environmental activities (Chang & Chen, 2012; Noh & Tolbert, 2019). It is the responsibility of university administrators to influence members of the organization to change the prevailing ethical and cultural pattern in a way that supports the emergence of a green organizational identity with social responsibility for members of the organization and the external community (Corley, 2004, Dillon & Manz, 2016). This is done by influencing organizational members in ways that supports organizational values and spreading an environmental culture that supports the shift towards a new organizational identity (Ashforth & Mael, 1989).

Green organizational identity is a comprehensive vision upon which managers rely on to direct their departments to the image that is desired by stakeholders internally and externally through strategic change (Soewarno et al., 2019, Song & Yu, 2017). Chang and Chen (2013) emphasized the importance of organizations adopting proactive strategies to carry out environmental management. It is also important for managers to change their business models and management mindsets to take advantage of green opportunities and to stimulate green innovation in the ecological era. Therefore, the introduction of green organizational identity and adoption of what supports the green environment, universities are considered one of the most prominent elements of transformation that must adopt and instill green organizational identity within their organizational identity (MacDonald, 2013).

Organizational identity in this context is defined as a process through which the organization's image and culture interact with each other (MacDonald, 2013). Many contemporary organizations have moved towards environmental management as part of a strategic planning process and have introduced green activities into their operational processes. Many green concepts have emerged in business management, such as green production, green marketing, green accounting, green innovation, and other concepts (Chang & Chen 2013, Song & Yu, 2017).

Many studies have proven that leading companies that practice environmental management have obtained competitive advantages as a result of consolidating their green organizational identity, as environmental considerations have become an integral part of the organizational identity and as one of the foundations of social responsibility (Noh & Tolbert, 2019; Song & Yu, 2017). Therefore, universities' adoption of a green organizational identity must be reflected in their current strategies.

Study Method:

The descriptive analytical method was used for this study. Previous literature related to the subject of this study and its variables was used as secondary sources with the aim of developing and building the theoretical framework. The questionnaire was used as a primary source to address the analytical aspects of the subject of this study. A questionnaire was developed to collect data related to the variables of this study, which included a number of paragraphs that reflected the objectives and questions of this study, which the respondents then answered.

A five-point Likert scale was used, where each answer was given relative importance according to the methods that were adopted for using this scale. The following equation was used to determine the level of importance of each dimension as follows: Category length = (highest value of answers - lowest value of answers)/number of levels of importance.

Class length= $(5-3)/3=1.33$.

The levels of importance are shown in the following table:

Table 1: Significance levels for arithmetic means

The Arithmetic Mean	Level of Importance
1.00-2.33	Low
2.34-3.66	Medium
3.67-5.00	High

Appropriate statistical methods were used to analyze the data of this study. The most prominent of these were descriptive statistics measures including the arithmetic means and standard deviations. Analytical statistical measures which included multiple regression were used to determine the effect of each dimension of quality culture on green organizational identity. Analytical statistical measures were also used to examine the moderating role of job satisfaction in the relationship between quality culture and green organizational identity in Private Jordanian universities.

Population and Study Sample:

The study population consisted of Dean of Colleges, Heads of academic departments, and Unit Directors in Private Jordanian universities. The facilitated sampling method was adopted for this study's population. 140 questionnaires were distributed and 109 questionnaires were recovered with a recovery rate of (77.8%). After a review, 9 questionnaires were excluded because they were not suitable for statistical analysis. Table No. (2) Shows the demographics characteristics of the study sample according to (gender, age, marital status, position at the university, years of service).

Table (2) is statement of the demographic characteristics of the study sample. The number of males in the sample were 79, with a percentage of (79%), while the number of females was 21, with a percentage of (21%). As for the distribution of the sample according to age it included the following: the number of sample members whose ages ranged between 30 to 40 years old was 7, with a percentage of 7%, while those whose ages ranged between 41 to 50 years old was 51, with a percentage of 51%. There were 42 sample members who were 50 years old or older, with a percentage of 42%. The distribution of the sample members according to marital status showed that the number of single individuals was 3, with a percentage of 3%. As for the married members of the sample, their number was 97 individuals, with a percentage of 97%. The distribution of the sample members according to their position as Deans of Colleges was 15, with a percentage of 15%.

The number of Heads of Academic department in the sample were 42 people, with a percentage of 42%. As for Unit Directors, their numbers were 43 individuals, with a percentage of 43%. The distribution of sample members' according to years of experience included the following: there were 4 individuals whose years of experience was less than 5 years, with a percentage of 4%. There was 20 sample member with 6 to10 years of experience, with a percentage of 20%. There were 49 individuals whose experience ranged between 10 to14 years, with a percentage of 49%. There were 27 individuals whose years of experience was more than 15 years, with a percentage of 27%.

Study Tool:

A questionnaire was developed as a tool to study and to collect the data. The questionnaire was presented to a group of academics for examination. The paragraphs of the questionnaire were modified to suit their comments. The questionnaire included the following four main parts: the first part included demographic characteristics, while the second part included items that measured the independent variable, which is quality culture and is represented by its dimensions (customer orientation, employee orientation, higher management commitment, process orientation, continuous improvement) which was developed through (Cronemyr et al., 2017), the third part of the questionnaire was related to the moderating variable job satisfaction. The items of this dimension were measured based on (Salau et al., 2018). The fourth part of the questionnaire relates to the dependent variable, green organizational identity, which was measured through (Soewarno et al., 2019).

Table 2

Variable	Category	Recurrence	Percentage
Gender	Male	79	79%
	Female	21	21%
Age	From 30 to 40 years old	7	7%
	From 41 to 50 years old	51	51%
	More than 50 years old	42	42%
Marital Status	Single	3	3%
	Married	97	97%
Position in the University	Dean	15	15%
	Head of Academic Department	42	42%
	Unit Director	43	43%
Years of Experience	Less than 5 years	4	4%
	From 6 to 10 years' experience	5	5%
	From 10 to 14 years' experience	49	49%
	15 years and more	27	27%
Total		100	100%

Stability of the Study Tool:

The internal consistency method (Cronbach Alpha) was used to calculate the reliability of the questionnaire. The Cronbach Alpha values for all variables and the questionnaire with all its items were higher than (0.6), which is considered an acceptable percentage in human and social studies (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016) and is shown in Table (3).

Table 3: Cronbach alpha values for this study's variables

Axis	Stability coefficient	Number of paragraphs
Orientation towards customer	0.888	4
Orientation towards employees	0.819	3
Management commitment	0.663	3
Process orientation	0.886	3
Continuous improvement	0.753	4
Job Satisfaction	0.805	4
Green organizational identify	0.721	4
The tool as a whole	0.933	25

Multicollinearity Test and Normal Distribution Test:

The multicollinearity test is one of the most important tests that must be performed before testing the hypotheses in order to ensure that there is no interference between the independent variables. The values of the variance inflation factor must also be less than 10. The results from Table No. (4) Indicates that the values of the inflation factor (The obtained VIF ranges between(1.441-2.242) is less than 10. Therefore, these variables do not suffer from the problem of multicollinearity. To verify that the data follows a normal distribution, the skewness coefficient was calculated. If the skewness value is less than (1) and (-1) means that the data follows a normal distribution. All values were less than (1), and therefore the data follows the normal distribution.

Table 4: Shows the Values of the Variance Inflation Factor and Permittivity

Variable	Tolerance	VIF	Skewness
Quality Culture Variables			
Orientation towards customer	0.461	2.171	-0.436
Orientation towards employees	0.517	1.934	-0.845
Management commitment	0.645	1.55	-0.142
Process orientation	0.446	2.242	-0.722
Continuous improvement	0.694	1.141	-0.903

Statistical Analysis:

Descriptive Statistics:

The results of descriptive statistics for this study's variables are shown in Table No. (5). The arithmetic means, standard deviations, and importance levels for each dimension of this study are shown. The highest dimensions in terms of arithmetic mean was continuous improvement which was (3.94) with a standard deviation of (0.61). This indicates that the respondents to this study tool believe that universities care about continuous improvement and motivating employees to participate. Job satisfaction had lowest dimensions in terms of the arithmetic mean, where the arithmetic mean was (2.21) with a standard deviation of (0.97). This indicates that the respondents to the questionnaire believe that the wage and incentive systems in Private Jordanian universities do not meet their requirements and that they believe these universities do not provide them with sufficient job satisfaction.

Table 5: Shows the Arithmetic Means, Standard Deviations, and Significance Levels of this Study's Variables

Number	Variable	Arithmetic mean	Standard Deviation	Level of importance
1	Orientation towards customer	3.85	0.84	High
2	Orientation towards employees	3.86	0.69	High
3	Management commitment	3.25	0.87	Medium
4	Process orientation	3.73	0.91	High
5	Continuous improvement	3.94	0.61	High
6	Job Satisfaction	2.21	0.97	Low
7	Green organizational identify	3.84	0.58	High

Testing the Study Hypotheses:

The researchers used the SPSSv23 program to test the hypotheses. The multiple linear regression test method was also used for the first main hypothesis. The hierarchical regression test was used on the second study hypothesis.

Ho1: There is no statistically significant effect of the dimensions of quality culture (customer orientation, employee orientation, higher management commitment, continuous improvement, process orientation) on green organizational identity in Private Jordanian universities.

Table No. (6) indicates that the results of the multiple linear regression test for the dimensions of quality culture (customer orientation, employee orientation, higher management commitment, process orientation, continuous improvement) on green organizational identity show that the value of the correlation coefficient was (0.642) which indicates that there is relationship between the independent and dependent variables that is positive and of medium strength.

The value of the coefficient of determination is (0.413). This means that (41.3%) of the variation occurring in the dependent variable is caused by the independent variables combined, and that (58.7%) of the variation occurring in the dependent variable is due to other reasons that were not examined in this study. As for the calculated F value, it was (13.205), and this value is greater than the tabular value at the significance level of (0.000).

This level is less than the statistical significance level of (0.05). Therefore, this model is a significant and valid model for interpreting the effect on the dependent variable. As for this study's hypotheses, the beta value for the customer orientation dimension was (0.145). This value indicates the existence of a positive relationship between the two variables. The calculated T value was (1.804), and this value was smaller than the tabular value of (1.96) and the level of statistical significance was (0.074).

This level was greater than the level of statistical significance at the level of (0.05), and therefore the statistical ruling is to accept the null hypothesis that there is no statistically significant effect of customer orientation on green organizational identity in Private Jordanian universities. As for the orientation towards employees, the beta value was (0.216) and the calculated T value was (2.346).

This value is greater than the tabular value of (1.96) and the level of statistical significance is (0.021). This level is smaller than the level of statistical significance at the level of (0.05), and therefore the Zero hypothesis is rejected with a statistically significant effect of employee orientation on the organizational identity in Private Jordanian Universities. As for the dimension of higher management commitment on green organizational identity, the beta value was (0.086) and the calculated T value was (1.316).

This value is smaller than the tabulated T value of (1.96). The level of statistical significance is (0.191), and therefore the null hypothesis is accepted that there is no effect of higher management commitment on green organizational identity. The results of the statistical analysis also indicated that there was no statistically significant effect of the process orientation dimension on the green organizational identity, as the calculated T value was (-0.103) and the level of statistical significance was (0.918).

As for continuous improvement, the beta value was (0.221) and the calculated T value was 2.452 and its level of significance is 0.016. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted that there is a statistically significant effect of the continuous improvement dimension on the green organizational identity in Private Jordanian universities.

Table 6: Results of the Multiple Linear Regression Test Analysis of the Dimensions of Quality Culture on Green Organizational Identity

R Link	The coefficient of determination	F Value	Significance level	
0.42	0.413	13.205	0	
Dimensions of quality culture	B	Standard error	T value	Significance level
Orientation towards customer	0.145	0.081	1.804	0.074
Orientation towards employees	0.216	0.092	2.346	0.021
Management commitment	0.086	0.066	1.316	0.191
Process orientation	-0.008	0.075	-0.103	0.918
Continuous improvement	0.221	0.09	2.452	0.016

The Second Main Hypothesis:

Ho2: There is no statistically significant effect of quality culture on organizational identity with job satisfaction as a moderating variable in Private Jordanian Universities.

To test this hypothesis, a hierarchical linear regression test was used, where the independent variable and the dependent variable were entered in one step. The interaction between these two variables was then entered in the second step. Table (7) shows the hierarchical linear regression test, which consists of two steps or two models. The F value for the first model was (29.817) and the significance level was (0.000).

This indicates that the first model was a significant model, and the F value calculated for the second model was (26.441) and the significance level was (0.000). This also indicates the significance of the regression model. The correlation coefficients in the first model were (0.617) and in the second model were (0.673).

This indicates an improvement in the correlation of the independent and adjusted variables with the dependent variable. As for the coefficient of determination in the first model was (0.381) while the second model was (0.452). This indicates a high percentage of interpretation obtained on the dependent variable in the presence of the moderating variable (job satisfaction).

This change was positive with a value of (0.072). As for the beta values for the interaction between quality culture and job satisfaction were (0.153), and the calculated T value was (3.546). This value is greater than the tabular value of (1.96), and the level of statistical significance is (0.001).

This level is less than the level of statistical significance at the level of (0.05), which indicates that job satisfaction positively improves the relationship between quality culture and green organizational identity in Private Jordanian Universities.

Table 7: shows the hierarchical regression test of the moderating role of job satisfaction between quality culture and green organizational identity

Independent Variable	The First Step			The Second Step		
	B	Calculated T Value	Sig.	B	Calculated T Value	Sig.
Quality Culture	0.36	7.717	0	0.383	8.592	0
Job Satisfaction	0.004	0.087	0.931	0.005	0.114	0.91
Quality Culture * Job Satisfaction		0.153	3.546	0.001		
R	0.617	0.673				
R ²	0.381	0.452				
R ²	-	0.072				
F	29.817	26.441				
Sig F	0	0				

The following figure shows the interaction between quality culture and job satisfaction on green organizational identity.

DISCUSSING THE RESULTS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Several results were reached through the statistical analysis of this study's hypotheses and questions. The most prominent results were the following: First, the results of this study showed that the level of quality culture was high, as the arithmetic averages for the dimensions of quality culture ranged between (3.25-3.94). This indicates that the practice of quality culture in Private Jordanian Universities, from the point of view of respondents of the questionnaire, is high, and these universities focus on continuous improvement and orientation towards organizational values that support quality culture.

Second: The results of this study confirmed that the level of green organizational identity was high, as the arithmetic mean for this variable was (3.84). This indicates that the respondents to the questionnaire believe that Private Jordanian Universities have begun to pay attention to green practices, such as producing electricity through solar panels, and that university administrations are interested in building a green organizational identity.

Third: The results of this study showed that there is a statistically significant effect of the employee orientation and continuous improvement on green organizational identity. This result may be attributed to the fact that the universities' interest in continuous improvement will lead to improving the image of universities with regard to the environmental and green aspects of the organization. The results of this study agreed with the results of (Bingol et al., 2013), which emphasizes the role of organizational culture in organizational identity.

Fourth: The results of this study showed that there is no statistically significant effect of the dimensions of quality culture (customer orientation, process orientation, higher management commitment) on green organizational identity. This result may be due to the overwhelming interest of private university administrations in organizational identity based on academic reputation to a greater extent than green organizational identity. Therefore, universities' customer orientation will be about the costs of study and the quality of education, and this also applies to the administration's commitment to pay more attention to the educational and academic process.

Fifth: The results of this study confirmed that job satisfaction improves the relationship between quality culture and green organizational identity in Private Jordanian Universities. The results are in agreement with many studies that confirm that job satisfaction plays a moderating role and improves the relationship between the variables examined by these studies (TURUNÇ and ÇALIŞKAN,2018; TURGUT et al.,2017)

Despite the importance of the results that were reached by this study, there were some limitations that must be taken into consideration when generalizing its results. These limitations can form a window for future studies that will be broader in scope. The most important of these limitations is this study was limited to Private Jordanian Universities, and that the unit of analysis and sampling is limited to specific groups which were employees in private universities (Deans, Heads of academic departments, and Unit directors). The researchers were also forced to use a convenient sample to conduct this study.

In light of the findings of this study, it is recommended that administrators of Private Jordanian universities give attention and importance to spreading a quality culture that supports building a green organizational identity in addition to a focus on raising the level of job satisfaction among employees in Private Jordanian universities to improve the image of their green organizational identity. The recommendations also include putting environmental concerns in the vision and the strategy of these universities in a way that enhances their level of evaluation and raises their level of competitiveness.

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